

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN STRUCTURAL DIMENSIONS AND CAREER PATH DEVELOPMENT

RELACIÓN ENTRE DIMENSIONES ESTRUCTURALES Y DESARROLLO DE RUTA PROFESIONAL

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RESUMEN

El objetivo de este estudio fue explicar la relación entre las dimensiones estructurales y el desarrollo de la carrera profesional. Este estudio fue un estudio aplicado en términos de objetivo y fue explicativo en términos del método de recolección de datos. El desarrollo de la trayectoria profesional como parte de un sistema organizacional integral para el desarrollo y el progreso en las organizaciones del tercer milenio requiere el aprendizaje continuo y la mejora continua de las personas, organizaciones y grupos de trabajo e integrarlo con la estrategia y el esfuerzo organizacional de todos los miembros de la organización.

Palabras clave: Dimensiones estructurales, Desarrollo de trayectoria profesional.

ABSTRACT

The aim of this study was to explain the relationship between structural dimensions and career path development. This study was an applied study in terms of objective and was explanatory in terms of data collection method. Career path development as part of a comprehensive organizational system for the development and progress in third millennium organizations requires the continuous learning and continuous improvement of individuals, organizations and working groups and integrating it with the organizational strategy and effort of all members of the organization.

Keywords: Structural dimensions, Career path development.

Fecha de recepción: noviembre 2019

Fecha de aprobación: febrero 2019

DOI:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8118206>

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INTRODUCTION

In today's world, economic power and prosperity of each country depends on the optimal use of facilities, industries and, especially the human resources of that country. Qualified and skilled human resource is a valuable asset to the growth and development of organizations and countries, and is the largest capital of a country and the main factor for its development (Newman, Bimrose, Nielsen & Zacher, 2018).

In recent years, professional experts' paying attention to human resource management issues has created plans to improve the career path of employees. Some of the leading companies have developed plans to improve career path and some other organizations pay attention to career path only to manage the employees and they argue that traditional and conventional way of recruiting does not contribute to the progress of employees and does not improve their service status. They argue that employees need to be evolved and they need to acquire new skills since skilled, experienced, knowledgeable, and motivated employees are essential to the success of any organization and they should not be ignored. Organizational commitment of employees in the long term, depends on the fact to what extent they are feeling success in the organization (Kline, 2019; Lacasse, 2018). To ensure the survival of the organization, managers must attract talents and elites and provide the conditions for their development. In organizations, an employee's career plan focuses not only on employees' career, but also on all aspects, processes, attitudes, behaviors and affairs related to employee's work lives (Cort, 2018).

In past, work, capital and land were considered as the main factors of production, but human resource technology and increased productivity were considered as growth and developmental factors. The career path as a factor in human resource efficiency, creates life and career experiences that have a particular impact on people's thoughts, values and motivations, leading to perfection in people (Van der Horst, 2018).

On the other hand, none of the human resources' plans will succeed without considering the career goals of the employees. Career path planning is a process in which a person clarifies his personal career goals during his or her work life and always behaves in such a way that he can finally achieve all these goals and can manage the career path of the process to make decision to accept or reject work opportunities for employees (Hiller, 2017). Human resource planning involves assessing the current and future needs of the organization, which should be performed by relying on current resources and possible future resources. All organizations consider the human resources as a key factor. Managers of organization are trying to create a motivation for their employees, so that they can

create a sense of satisfaction in their employees and the organization can use the power, skill, knowledge and expertise of the employees to achieve its goals (Arbuckle, 2016).

Additionally, the success of the organization depends on its employees and having right people to be employed at right jobs and in right situations, which is very effective in the growth and survival of the organization (Ismail, 2017). Hence, human resources specialists must pay special attention to organizational conditions and type of organizational structure as well as the organizational goals. Thus, it is necessary to pay special attention to the process of employees' progress and to carefully monitor their progress in a logical and precise manner in order to achieve the individual and organizational goals (Hyrkas, 2015). In fact, the career path and career progress are not accidental and it should be planned based on specific criteria and organizational criteria and according to the interest and capabilities of individuals in order to motivate employees (Van der Horst, 2018). Nowadays, the value of employees has also changed because organizations expect more self-actualization of them. They tend to have employees involved in planning their career paths and they create the opportunity for them to make an effort to achieve career growth (Hannes, 2018; Harrington, 2015). Therefore, the planning and implementation of the career path development is expected to be considered in the organizations, because the employees will no longer accept that they will achieve their goal merely through organizational promotions (Wehrle & Kira, 2018).

In past, organizations focused on career path management, but employees have nowadays recognized the importance of this issue and have focused on it. In the traditional career path of management models or centralized models, the employees' career path was under the responsibility of organizational management and the movement at the organization level was vertical and the goal of employees was organizational promotion and increasing the salaries. In the past, the question for organizations was what expectations they should have from their employees, but they nowadays, they have to ask themselves how they can make the individuals accept jobs in their organization. Moreover, employees are not restricted to an organization or organizational unit in the management of their career path. Accordingly, considering the importance of career path in staff performance, this study was conducted to determine if there is a relationship between organizational structure and career path.

RESEARCH LITERATURE

The success of organizations, especially public organizations, and organizations that deal with a large number of clients, depends on its employees or its human resources. Competitiveness and the growth and survival of organizations depend

on the availability of skilled human resources and the use of these capitals in right careers and right times. Managers of organizations are trying to create motivation in their human resources so that they can see the best and most desirable performance of their employees and finally facilitate the achievement of the long-term goals of the organization.

The growth and development of organizations is not possible without regarding to human capitals and labor force. All organizations pay attention to human resources as key and essential assets of the organization. Organizational leaders are trying to motivate people to achieve their organization goals in their human resources. In addition, desirable performance is the ultimate goal of any organization. Creating the motivation in employees and finally achieving desirable performance is one of the main concerns of senior managers of the organizations. The performance-based payment method is one of the well-known methods of managers leading to motivation in human resources.

In this method, to motivate, the employee salary is determined based on his level of performance. Career improvement path explaining plan is one of the performance-based payment plans in which employees receive extra salary for their performance. Career path development is a series of individual attitudes and behaviors related to career during the career life. As all people in all occupations and positions learn unique experiences, so each individual pursues a unique career path that allows them to make decisions in their work life.

Career path development in an organization such as bank has high importance. In order to motivate and improve the efficiency of the employees and to improve the quality of banking services, observing the career path development guideline is essential. Due to the sensitivity of banking activities and the relationship of employees with customers, it is important for bank employees to gain the best feedback from customers. Career path promotion is a factor that can improve the performance of the bank and make customers satisfied. Given the importance of this issue, the conceptual foundations and the theoretical framework of the research have been presented as follows:

The career path model is based on (Miller & Brickman, 2017) research. After longitudinal study on a career path of a group of Massachusetts Institute of Technology of managers and students and creating a concept of career path orientations, (Miller & Brickman, 2017) categorized it into the following general dimensions: Technical and functional competencies, management competencies, independence / lack of dependency, security / stability, sense of service / sacrifice, pure challenge, integrated lifestyle, entrepreneurial innovation.

METHODOLOGY

Data analysis at the level of descriptive statistics (frequency, mean, standard deviation, minimum, maximum, table and chart) and inferential statistics (Mahalanobis test and Pearson correlation) was performed using SPSS, version 23, software and structural equation modeling method and AMOS 23 software. In order to evaluate the proposed model, the two-step approach was used.

It allows the researcher to test a set of regression equations simultaneously. Structural equation modeling is a comprehensive approach for testing hypotheses about the relationships of the observed and latent variables. Sometimes, covariance structural analysis is called as causal modeling, but the mostly-used and known term for it, is structural equation modeling or SEM. (Santilli, Nota & Hartung 2018) methods were used to test the intermediary relationships in their proposed model.

The fit adequacy of proposed model was examined by several fit indices. These indices include: chi-square index, normed square index (Chi-square ratio to degrees of freedom), goodness-of-fit index (GFI), adjusted goodness-of-fit index (AGFI), normed fit index (NFI), comparative fit index (CFI), incremental fit index (IFI), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), and Root-mean-square error of approximation (RMSEA).

RESULTS

A model was presented to test the research hypotheses on the relationship between the components of structural dimensions (concentration, complexity and formality) and career path development in Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran.

Table 1. Goodness of fit indices for testing the first three sub-hypotheses of the research

Fit indices of model	CMIN	DF	CMIN/DF	NPAR	P	GFI	AGFI	IFI	TLI	CFI	NFI	RMSEA
Fitted model	194.44	181	1.07	95	0.234	0.93	0.90	0.99	0.99	0.99	0.92	0.018
Desirable values	= df	–	< 3	–	>0.05	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	<0.08

Resource: Authors,2019

The results of the above model test (Table 1) showed that the relationship between concentration and career path development in branches of Sina Bank in the

southeast of Iran was positive and significant ($P < 0.05$, $t = 5.44$, $\beta = 0.73$). The relationship between complexity and career path development of branches of Sina Bank in the southeast of Iran was also positive and significant ($P < 0.05$, $t = 4.32$, $\beta = 0.43$). The relationship between formality and career path development of branches of Sina Bank in the southeast of Iran was also positive and significant ($P < 0.05$, $t = 2.51$, $\beta = 0.18$). Regarding the fit analysis of the model based on fitness indicators, it can be stated that the factor analysis model had suitable fit for testing the hypotheses. In other words, due to the suitability of fit indices, this model can be used to examine the relationship between the components of structural dimensions (concentration, complexity and formality) and career path development of Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran in.

Table 2. Relationship between the latent variables

Paths	Path coefficients			Significance level
	Standardized parameter	No-standardized parameter	T value	
Centralization → career path development	0.73	0.55	5.44	0.001
Complexity → career path development	0.43	0.25	4.32	0.001
Formality → career path development	0.18	0.13	2.51	0.012

Resource: Authors, 2019

In (Table 2) with regard to fit analysis of the model based on fit indices, it can be said that the factor analysis model had suitable fit for testing the hypotheses. In other words, due to suitability of fit indices, this model can be used to examine the relationship between the components of structural dimensions (concentration, complexity and formality) with the first component of the career path development (creativity and innovation) of Sina Bank branches in the in the southeast of Iran in.

Table 3. Goodness of fit indices of structural model for testing the second three sub-hypothesis of research

Model fitness indicators	CMIN	DF	CMIN/DF	NPAR	P	GFI	AGFI	IFI	TLI	CFI	NFI	RMSEA
The fitted model	158.19	136	1.16	74	0.094	0.94	0.90	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.92	0.027
Favorable values	- df	—	<3	—	>0.05	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	<0.08

Resource: Authors, 2019

The results of the above model test (Table 3) showed that the relationship between concentration and creativity and innovation in branches of Sina Bank in the southeast of the Iran was positive and significant ($P < 0.05$, $t = 2.11$, $\beta = 0.20$). The relationship between complexity and creativity and innovation in branches of Sina Bank in the southeast of Iran was also positive and significant ($P < 0.05$, $t = 2.59$, $\beta = 0.30$). The relationship between formality and creativity and innovation in Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran was not significant ($P > 0.05$, $t = 0.53$, $\beta = 0.05$).

Table 4. Relationship between latent variables

Paths	Path coefficients			Significance level
	Standardized parameter	No-standardized parameter	T value	
Centralization → creativity and innovation	0.20	0.15	2.11	0.035
Complexity → creativity and innovation	0.30	0.25	2.59	0.010
Formality → creativity and innovation	0.05	0.05	0.53	0.593

Resource: Authors, 2019

With regard to fit analysis of the model based on fit indices, it can be stated that the factor analysis model had suitable fit for testing the hypotheses. In other words, due to suitability of fit indices, this model can be used to examine the relationship between the components of structural dimensions (concentration, complexity and formality) and the second component of the career path development (functional

and management technical competencies) of Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran.

Table 5. Goodness of fit indices of structural model for testing the third three sub-hypotheses of the research

Fit indices of model	CMIN	DF	CMIN/DF	NPAR	P	GFI	AGFI	IFI	TLI	CFI	NFI	RMSEA
Fitted model	587.82	385	1.53	111	0.001	0.86	0.82	0.94	0.93	0.94	0.85	0.049
Desirable values	= df	–	< 3	–	>0.05	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	<0.08

Resource: Authors, 2019

The results of the above model test (Table 5) showed that the relationship between concentration and functional and management technical competencies of Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran was significant and positive ($P < 0.05$, $t = 6.22$, $\beta = 0.67$). The relationship between complexity and functional and management technical competencies of Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran was positive and significant ($P < 0.05$, $t = 4.37$, $\beta = 0.44$). The relationship between formality and functional and management technical competencies of Bank Sina branches in the southeast of Iran was positive and significant ($P > 0.05$, $t = 2.96$, $\beta = 0.23$).

Table 6. Relationship between the latent variables

Paths	Path coefficients			Significance level
	Standardized parameter	No-standardized parameter	T value	
Centralization → Technical, functional, and managerial competencies	0.67	0.56	6.22	0.001
Complexity → Technical, functional, and managerial competencies	0.44	0.39	374	0.001
Formality → Technical, functional, and managerial competencies	0.23	0.24	2.96	0.003

Resource: Authors, 2019

With regard to fit analysis of the model based on fit indices, it can be said that the factor analysis model had suitable fit for testing the hypotheses. In other words, due to suitability of fit indices, this model can be used to examine the relationship

between the components of structural dimensions (concentration, complexity and formality) and the third component of the career path (security and stability) of Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran in (Table 7).

Table 7. Goodness of fit indices of structural model for testing the fourth three sub-hypotheses of the research

Fit indices of model	CMIN	DF	CMIN/DF	NPAR	P	GFI	AGFI	IFI	TLI	CFI	NFI	RMSEA
Fitted model	156.71	131	1.20	79	0.062	0.94	0.90	0.99	0.98	0.98	0.92	0.030
Desirable values	= df	–	< 3	–	>0.05	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	>0.90	<0.08

Resource: Authors, 2019

The results of the above model test (Table 8) showed that the relationship between concentration and security and stability of Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran was not significant ($P > 0.05$, $t = 1.72$, $\beta = 0.18$). The relationship between complexity and security and stability of the Sinai Bank branches in the southeast of Iran was not significant ($P > 0.05$, $t = 0.40$, $\beta = 0.05$). The relationship between formality and security and stability of Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran was not significant ($P > 0.05$, $t = -0.37$, $\beta = -0.04$)

DISCUSSION

Career path development as part of a comprehensive organizational system for the development and progress in third millennium organizations requires the continuous learning and continuous improvement of individuals, organizations and working groups and integrating it with the organizational strategy and effort of all members of the organization. It provides many opportunities for organizations through strategic development system. In addition, achieving flexible goals requires programs that create conditions to achieve the goals. In addition, concentration on the relationship between organizational structure and the development of the career path, existence of efficient human resource is one of the most important issues in current organizations. Each system tries to maximize its efficiency and human resource development is critical to achieve the organizational success.

The results of the main hypothesis test showed that there was a significant relationship between organizational structure and career path development, since employees nowadays are thinking and concerned with their profession. They are looking for long-term, challenging and reliable careers and they tend to grow and develop in their careers. Additionally, employees often initiate their careers with the hope of achieving special goals in the organization. Most of them pay great

attention to the ways of reaching to progress, strength, and maximum rewards and responsibilities. The results of this research were in line with the results of the research conducted by (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2017).

The results of the first hypothesis test indicated that there was a significant relationship between the concentration and career path development. As concentration deals with the distribution of authority in the organization and determines who has the right to make decisions and accepting the distribution of authority in the organization by the employees leads identifying and studying their interests, values, strengths and weaknesses in the organization, and opportunities and existing threats. Accordingly, they can set their career development path to achieve their pre-determined goals. The results of this research was in line with the results of the research conducted by (Waltz & Bausell, 2015).

The results of the second hypothesis test showed that there was a significant relationship between the complexity and the career path development, since when the organization needs high level of knowledge and skills, complexity increases and communication and coordination become difficult. However, it seems that employees of Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran often initiate their career with the hope of achieving special goals in the organization and most of them considered it important for progress, authority and maximum rewards and responsibilities. The results of this research were in line with the results of the research conducted by (Hyrkas, 2015). The results of the third hypothesis test of the research showed that there was a significant relationship between the formality and career path development. The result indicates that the authorities of Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran have observed some restrictions so that this organization can rely on laws, regulations, and procedures to orient the behavior of their employees. It has caused that employees of this organization undertake some roles and duties their work life to achieve their goals, hopes and wishes. The results of this research were in line with the results of the research conducted by (Santilli et al., 2018).

There was a significant relationship between concentration and creativity and innovation. Concentration deals with the distribution of authority within the organization and determines who has the right to make decisions and to accept the distribution of authority in the organization by the employee; it has been effective in the use of creative thinking that can be created within the organization. Based on the researcher's reviews, no research was found to examine the relationship between concentration and creativity and innovation, so it was not possible to compare the results by the researcher.

There was a significant relationship between complexity and creativity and innovation, as when the organization needs high level of knowledge and skills,

complexity increases and communication and coordination become difficult. However, it seems that Sina bank employees in the southeast of Iran have thought on creating new ideas to improve and enhance the quality and quantity of organization and innovation activities. According to researcher's reviews, no study was found to examine the relationship between complexity and creativity and innovation, so it was not possible to compare the results by the researcher.

There was no significant relationship between creativity and innovation. This result might suggest that Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran have not been able to enhance the creativity and innovation of their employees. Based on the researcher's reviews, no study was found to examine the relationship between formality and creativity and innovation, so it was not possible to compare the results by the researcher.

As concentration deals with distribution of authority within the organization, it determines who has the right to make decisions; it seems that Sinai Bank branches in the southeast of Iran have their own deputies, managements, and units that have their own tasks and activities. Based on the researcher's reviews, no study was found to examine the relationship between concentration and functional and management technical competencies, so it was not possible to compare the results by the researcher.

As the complexity is a degree of specialization of individuals based on their career expertise within the organization, it has made Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran to enable their collective and individual capabilities, employees and teams to successfully carry out the tasks assigned for them. According to researcher's reviews, no study was found to examine the relationship between complexity and functional and management technical competencies, so it was not possible to compare the results by the researcher.

CONCLUSION

This result might suggest that Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran have been able to standardize the organizational careers to some extent and it has made organizations to have deputies, managements and units which have their own responsibilities and activities, according to their organizational chart. Based on researcher's review, no research was found to examine the relationship between formality and functional and management technical competencies, so it was not possible to compare the findings by the researcher.

As concentration deals with distribution of authority in the organization and determines who has the right to make decisions and accepting this authority by employees in the organization has caused organization not to be dependent on

people. It means that organization has not been able to provide the necessary conditions for empowering its employees in specialized dimensions, practical courage, experiencing, job satisfaction, communication, and thinking and work conscience so that employees can meet the specialized and social expectations and thus have career stability. According to researcher's reviews, no research was found to examine the relationship between concentration and security and stability, so it was not possible to compare the results by the researcher.

Bank branches in the southeast of Iran need high level of knowledge and skills, so the complexity has increased and communication and coordination have become difficult and as a result the organization has not been able to provide the necessary conditions to empower its employees in specialized dimensions, practical courage, experiencing, job satisfaction, behavior, communication, thinking and work conscience. According to researcher's reviews, no research was found to examine the relationship between complexity and security and stability, so it was not possible to compare the results by the researcher.

Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran have not been able to standardize their organizational jobs to provide the necessary conditions to empower their employees in specialized dimensions, practical courage, experiencing, job satisfaction, behavior, communication, thinking, and work conscience. Based on the researcher's reviews, no research was found to examine the relationship between formality and security and stability, so it was not possible to compare the results by the researcher.

The level of flexibility in decision-making and evaluation of activities in concentrated way in the Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran has not been able to provide help and counselling for those who buy the goods or services in that organization. According to researcher's reviews, no study was found to investigate the relationship between concentration and servicing, so it was not possible to compare the results by the researcher.

In Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran, the specialization of individuals in terms of job expertise within the organization has not been able to provide distinct services for customers based on the efficiency of the organization and according to the expectations of the customers in order to increase the profitability of the organization and affect the loyalty of its customers. According to the researcher's reviews, no study was found to examine the relationship between complexity and servicing, so it was not possible to compare the results by the researcher.

The degree of flexibility in decision-making and evaluating activities in concentrated manner in Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran has made its managers not to be able to show their respect for employees with respectful

behavior and sympathetic dialogue with people and establish visual communication with them. According to the researcher's reviews, no study was conducted to examine the relationship between concentration and self-esteem, so it was not possible to compare the results by the researcher.

Sina Bank branches in the southeast of Iran need high level of knowledge and skills, so complexity has increased and communication and coordination has become difficult. As a result, the organization has not been able to create an environment to enhance the self-esteem of the employees. According to the researcher's reviews, no study was found to examine the relationship between complexity and self-esteem, so it was not possible to compare the results by the researcher.

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